

Impact of Migration Women on Economic and Social Development: A Review of Evidence and Emerging Issues

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Abstract

This paper is discussed on the evidences and emerging issues of female migrants working in construction and brick kiln in Chennai-the second largest industry in India and one which employs almost 30 million people, approximately 30 percent of which are women, many of them migrants. In this paper, I extend beyond an empirical description of female migrant workers in the field of construction and brick kiln, considering the subjective and nuanced realities linked to women's lived experiences as migrants. Case studies were also conducted to explore the socio-economic status and experiences at the destination of migrant women at brick kiln at Red hills, Chennai.

Keywords: Interstate migration, Brick kiln workers.

Introduction

Some dream to escape the realities of life while others dream to face those realities in life. Throughout history of humanity, migration has been a fact of life. The reason people migrate are varied and often complex. Some people move to new places or countries to improve their economic situation or pursue their educations, or to escape human right violation such as abuse, torture, persecution, armed conflict, extreme poverty and even death, environmental crisis and etc. Indeed, their journey of migration can be full of danger. People still take the risk of migrating with lots of hope to have better life. While migrating some face detentions. Many face daily racism, xenophobia, psycho-social discriminations and injustice in all possible manners. They are uniquely vulnerable, especially women, without the usual support from society and state. With a small background of migration, a research article has been written in this paper.

Objective of the Article

The objectives of the article is to (1) explore the social conditions and problems faced by the women migrant workers in an construction and in brick kiln at Red hills and in Sriperumbudur, Chennai (2) study about the economic situations of migrant women.

Review of literature and methodology: It has been devoted to present a brief review of the literature related to the study and the methodology followed by the study.

Blume (2002). In his studies examine smigration is an issue that affects the dignity of individual person and society. The migrant faces lots of challenges and cries out for justice, requires solidarity, coordinated social- actions that could promote the human dignity, solidarity, and common good at national and international level. Every human person has an inalienable right to life and the activities needed to sustain and develop it.

Bhubaneswaron (2008:6). In this paper investigates about one third of the migrant households are landless and they depend on agricultural and non-agricultural wage labour. The underdeveloped agricultural economy of the state which makes its population unemployed in lean season creates a deficit household economy, which gets further accentuated due to persistent natural disasters such as droughts, low rainfall, and reduction of forest resources in tribal areas. Along with this, globalization has resulted in reduced market facilities and lack of employment opportunities for people.

Bhubaneswaron (2008:68-69). In this paper explores that interstate migrants do remit their money back home mostly through bank or post office The migrant men and women do not have any insurance or registration, and hence on death, the owner of the construction or the government gives no compensation to the kith and kin left behind. In addition, in the changed environment, the food habits, water, sanitation and the workload badly affect the health of the migrants. They are affected by different diseases like diarrhea, dehydration and fever frequently.

Bhubaneswaron (2008:67-68). states that Migration affects women in a myriad of ways. The women migrants themselves are affected within the process of migration- economically, socially particularly in health aspect, psychologically and also in extreme instances physically and sexually. 69% of the construction migration labours have their family income below Rs.10000. Women's earnings are affected by gender prejudices, stereotyped roles and double burden in family. The migrant woman has no scope of ownership on the value of her labour input towards the family income

Bhagat, (2012). argues that the informal sectors operation beyond the legal and institutional framework. The characteristics of the informal sector remain unchanged: low capital, micro-enterprises with less sophisticated technologies and marked by low wages to labour who work without contracts and protection. Some of the important sectors in which migrants work include: construction, brick kiln, salt pans, carpet and embroidery, commercial and plantation agriculture and variety of jobs in urban informal sectors such as vendors, hawkers, rickshaw puller, daily wage workers and domestic work.

IndraniMazumdar (2013:59) seeks to analyse at their destinations, 76% of all the women migrant workers (rural + urban) did not have any ration card, 16% had below poverty line (BPL) cards, less than half a per cent had Antyodaya cards and 7% had above poverty line (APL) cards

UNESCO (2013). paper reflects on devoid of social security and legal protection, they work in poor conditions and face labour market discrimination. Minimum wages are often flouted and employers bear no responsibility for health, shelter and other basic requirements of migrants.

Access to several government schemes like RashtriyaSwasthyaBimayojana(RSBY) and Public Distribution System (PDS) is not possible 91% of the women migrant workers had never availed of any public housing scheme, 79% had no National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) job cards, and 96% had never been employed under any public employment programme or scheme (IndraniMazumdar 2013:59).

S.Chandrasekhar (2014:6). In this paper explains lack of collateral limits the ability of agricultural labourers to borrow. As per the Census of India 2011, less than 40 percent of households availed banking services in large parts of Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Orissa, West Bengal, Jharkhand, Bihar, and North East. These states have a large number of households whose members work primarily as labourers. They are landless, poor and hence tend to migrate. As it is well known, these states account for a large share of short-term migrants. Financial inclusion alone will not translate into credit worthiness. If lack of access to land constrains progress in access to credit markets then it is a cause for concern since land is scarce and hence linkages with insurance and pension products as well.

AmjumShaheen et al (2016:240). In their work states that urban centers with new developments work requiring semi-skilled workers at as pull factors for them. Construction activities include building schools, hospitals, houses, offices, township, highways, roads, ports, airports, railways power projects and so on. Nearly 80 per cent of the workers involved in the working of construction and unorganized sector work on contract basis.

Nishikantsingh et al. (2016:177). In their study states that migration from rural to urban is more dominating than urban to urban streams.

AnjumShaheen et al (2016:240-243).In their study found that the most of the migrant were paid as daily wages, regardless of the numbers of hours, with 19 of the respondent s reporting sub-minimum wages. Most of them work for 10 to 12 hours and usually hours fixed by the government is violated.Women were paid less eramounting to Rs.120 per day only based on eight hours of work.

From the review of earlier literature, the following research gaps have been identified. It was observed that a number of studies were conducted and analyzed on issues of women migration, agricultural wages, insurance, registration, gender prejudices, double burden in family, information sectors, BPL, social security, legal protection, credit, pull factors and unorganized sectors work. In view of the research gaps enumerated in the aforesaid paragraph, the researcher had intended to undertake an in-depth study on impact of migration women on economic and social development with two case studies.

Methodology

The study employs mixed method using the qualitative and quantitative secondary data in looking into the misery for interstate migration women working in construction and brick kiln in and around Chennai area.

Research Design: Qualitative research design (Case study method is used).

Sampling Design: Two case studies

Tool: Structured interview schedule was used with open ended questions.

Case Studies

Case Study No:1 My name is Prabitrajal, 37 years old, Place: Bolangir District, Orissa. We six people stay here in one room (made out of Asbestos cement sheet. 10 x 8 Sqft) which includes me, my husband, my two children, my brother in law and his new wife. This is my second year staying and working outside of my village. My day starts at 5:30 am in the morning and the work time is till 5:30 pm in the evening. Yes I have to get up even early to finish my household works and cook food for lunch. First I get paid with a total amount of Rs 15000/- for a period of 6 months and they I have to follow the contractors words where ever he take us for work. This is the agreement that I have to give my work without a daily wages till 6 months. For the daily expenses I get paid of Rs 300 per week. By this Rs.300 I have to bear the daily expenses. These days we are paid Rs.350 to 400, it depends on our production of brick kilns.

Case Study No: 2 I am Umesh UBasi. I am living with my husband and child in this room, which is made of asbestos cement sheet. My boy child is four years old and stays with us now. We came here with the help of our family relative. My husband is very sickly and thus I have to work day and night to support my family. We are getting Rs.350 per day. I am not able to work daily due to my back pain. In this brick kiln company we ought carry things and frequently bend and carry bricks and its raw material. I like to go back home as early as possible but we don't have any livelihood over there. Here we have our relatives and friends are there and they are very helpful to us. The local people don't relate with us and we don't get much time to see them and talk to them.

Understanding migration and its impacts on migrant women

- Approximately 30 percent of which are women in the construction industry in India.
- Inter-state migration is about 11 million. The total interstate migrant is about 11 million of which 5.2 million males and 5.8 million females
- Orissa (41.6%) has a large number of migrant female laborers in search of livelihood in and around Chennai. 87 per cent of the women are migrating with the major reason of marriage, economic higher educational and higher social status.
- Women with low level of education migrate more for job.
- 69% if the construction migration labours have their family income below Rs.10000.
- The woman does not get a chance to get her part of the remittance. Usually the working hours and minimum wage fixed by the government is violated.
- Women do all the household work as well work in the migration site, it brings enormous amount of physical as well as the emotional pain as result of huge stress.
- The homogeneity of the family is disturbed. The family experiences constant change due to migration.
- The pregnant women & small babies suffer much. They are deprived of immunization and other nutritional benefits.
- Migrant workers brought on the contract which includes often working 10 hours days on an average, sheltering at working sites mostly and with four days holidays in a month.
- Migrant workforce largely controlled by a middle man who control their lives and livelihood. Denied access to health care facilities.

Suggestions

- A minimum wages should be provided irrespective of gender. There should be no wage disparity on the basis of gender.
- The policy regarding the job opportunities of migrants should be such that there may not exist any kind of bias at work place regarding gender preferences, i.e. women migrants must also be given equal and fair chance as their male counterparts and proper trust should be maintained over them.
- Migrant women empowerment the issues like low wages, nonpayment of wages, gender disparity in wages, forced sex work & trafficking, violence, domestic violence, exploitation of single women, lack of education & neglect of children's education, lack of health services for self as well as children, reproductive health issues, lack of identity papers, breakdown of social network such as self-help groups in the destination, social exclusion, non-application of registration of birth and marriages, food insecurity & malnutrition, no legal mechanism for protection, no awareness on rights and facilities of protection of migrations which are affecting women in the context of migration are. In this context, adequate measures must be taken by central and state government in order to protect the rights and dignity of migrant women. Usually the working hours and minimum wage fixed by the government is being violated.

Conclusion

The above analysis and collected reviews indicates that the life of the women is the worst in terms of poor economy, education, social security, inadequate policy, psychological problems, and poor social status. As a researcher we felt that migrant women workers have little or no knowledge of their basic rights, entitlements and bonded labour prohibitions. Being from the most vulnerable segments of society and lacking organization, bonded labourers remain “invisible” to the authorities. In this regard, the government and organization should play a major role in formulating the policy in favour of migrant women and providing employment possibilities at local and state level. When all these measures seriously are taking into consideration, there will be a great impact on economic and social development among women migration.

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